

Energy-Classical Frequency in Quantum Oscillator Part III

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In Parts I and II we noted that a quantum oscillator time-independent Schrodinger equation may be scaled such that $x \rightarrow y$ with $y = \sqrt{km}x$ and $E \rightarrow E\sqrt{m/k}$. Given that the LHS side is a function strictly of y which may be integrated from $-\infty$ to ∞ , the RHS must be independent of k and m . Thus E is proportional to $\sqrt{k/m}$ which “happens” to be the oscillator classical angular frequency. In Part II we noted that the scaling occurs in the Schrodinger equation because one uses $-i\hbar d/dx$ as the momentum operator which follows from the $\exp(ipx)$ form of a free particle wavefunction.

In this note, we show that for any equation: $a d^2/dx^2 W + b x W = E W$ scaling of the form $x \rightarrow y$ such that $y = \sqrt{b/a}x$ and $E \rightarrow E \sqrt{a/b}$ occurs. Furthermore if d/dx is associated with momentum then writing conservation of energy using $m/2 v^2$ leads to $1/a \cos^2(\omega t) + b \sin^2(\omega t) = b$ and ω is proportional to \sqrt{ab} . Thus E must be proportional to ω , the classical frequency. (An equation of the form $a df/dt + b f = \text{constant}$ must have a $\cos(\omega t)$ solution as is already known.)

We try to extend these ideas by considering a wave on a string with both ends fastened. The string produces sinusoidal waves, but sound is created if there is air. One may consider sound to come in identical units of energy proportional to the angular frequency ω . This is similar to the Planck blackbody radiation assumption about light. It may be shown that the string follows an oscillator solution because $d/dx dy/dx$ which represents the change in the $\sin(\theta)$ multiplied by the constant tension from x to $x+dx$ is set equal to y i.e Force is proportional to y which is the oscillator result. If one sets energy proportional to ω as in the case of light and wishes to have an equation strictly in x describing this scenario and also linked to energy conservation then the momentum squared term should have dimensions $1/x$. This suggests d/dx as a solution because E must be proportional to ω . Thus we argue that one may work “backwards” modeling phonons like photons in a classical problem to obtain the quantum operator $p = -i\hbar d/dx$ which is linked to the free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$.

Classical Oscillator

Consider the general conservation of energy equation for an oscillator with $x = f(t)$:

$$m/2 df/dt^2 + k/2 f^2 = E \quad ((1))$$

Taking d/dt of both sides one obtains: $0 = kf + m d/dt df/dt$ (Newton's second law) which yields $\cos(\omega t)$ (etc) as a solution. This result is well known.

Next taking the solution $\cos(\omega t)$ and using it in the general equation:

$$1/a \omega^2 \cos^2(\omega t) + b \sin^2(\omega t) = b \quad ((2)) \quad \rightarrow \quad \omega \text{ proportional to } \sqrt{ab}$$

Quantum Oscillator

If one considers the general time-independent Schrodinger equation:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{d}{dx} W + b x x W + E W \right) \quad ((3))$$

one may change variables $x \rightarrow y$ such that $yy = xx \sqrt{b/a}$. Note one has "a" instead of $1/a$ as kinetic energy $= \frac{p^2}{2m} = .5mvv$. In such a case ((3)) becomes:

$$\frac{d}{dy} \left(\frac{d}{dy} W_1(y) + yy W_1(y) \right) = E \sqrt{1/ba} W_1(y) \quad ((4))$$

The LHS may be integrated over dy from $-\infty$ to ∞ to yield a number not depending on k or m so E cannot depend on k or m i.e. E is proportional to \sqrt{ba} , but it was already shown in the previous section that the w the classical angular frequency is proportional to \sqrt{ba} in general so E must be proportional to w the classical angular frequency.

Wave on a String with Fastened Ends

We try to find a physical example which is linked to an oscillator and a classical frequency which constitutes energy. Consider a wave on a string with the ends fastened. The result is sinusoidal which follows from Newton's second law. In particular one obtains the wave equation because $.5m v v = .5 m \frac{dy}{dt} \frac{dy}{dt}$ where y is the height of the string from the horizontal. The force for a constant tension T in the string is:

$$T \sin(\theta) \text{ at } x+dx - T \sin(\theta) \text{ at } x = T \frac{d}{dx} (y(x+dx) - y(x)) = T \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dy}{dx}$$

As a result one has a wave equation: $\frac{1}{v} \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dy}{dt} = \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dy}{dx}$ where v is velocity dependent on T, m etc.

Separating variables $y(t,x) = y_1(t)y_2(x)$ leads to an equation of the form:

$$C y_2(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dy_2}{dx} \quad ((5))$$

but $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{dy_2}{dx}$ is proportional to force which is proportional to $y_2(x)$. This is the equation of an oscillator. The oscillator has a certain frequency and should create sound waves with this frequency if there is air. If one applies Planck's assumptions about blackbody light to phonons there should be an oscillator producing equal phonons each with energy proportional to w .

From the quantum oscillator result ((4)) we know that a conservation of energy type equation (time-independent Schrodinger equation) with an operator representing momentum i.e. acting on a function of x means that the operator should have dimensions $1/x$. One already knows that energy should be proportional to w because of the phonons produced. This requires a momentum operator with dimensions of $1/x$ suggesting $p \rightarrow -i\hbar \frac{d}{dx}$ when operating on $\exp(ipx)$.

Thus we argue that the classical problem of a wave on a string with fastened ends creating sound in air can point to the form of the quantum momentum operator if one insists on a

conservation of energy equation with E proportional to w (the sound frequency) and the existence of an x dependent operator which creates momentum when acting on a function $W(x)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion we note that given an equation of the form $a \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + b x x W + E W$ one may always scale $x \rightarrow y$ such that $yy = xx \sqrt{b/a}$ and $E \rightarrow E/\sqrt{ba}$. This implies that E must be proportional to \sqrt{b} because the LHS may be integrated over dy from $-\infty$ to ∞ yields a result independent of a and b . Similarly an oscillator conservation of energy equation $1/a w w \cos(wt)\cos(wt) + b \sin(wt)\sin(wt) = b$ implies that w is proportional to \sqrt{ab} . Thus E in the differential equation must be proportional to w , the classical oscillator frequency.

We try to apply these ideas to a string with ends fastened. The force is given as constant d/dx dy/dx , but this is set proportional to y (using separation of variables). This, however, is the oscillator equation. Thus an oscillator should produce sound in air with angular frequency w . Using the blackbody photon assumptions of Planck, one may argue that the phonon energy is proportional to w . Thus one has an oscillator which produces energy proportional to w (and not to $.5kAA$ a priori). If one wishes to apply a conservation of energy equation to the oscillator with an x related operator creating momentum when acting on a function $W(x)$, then in order to have energy proportional to w , the operator should have dimensions $1/x$. This suggests dy/dx for momentum or $-id/dx$ and $\exp(ipx)$ as an eigenfunction.. Thus we argue that using a classical problem one may see the quantum momentum operator form i.e $p \rightarrow -id/dx$ emerge